

ISSUES OF SENTENCING FOR THE PETTY GAMBLING AND GAMES BASED ON RISK

Beristenov Samat Orazbaevich

Head of the Organization Department of the Ministry
of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan,

E-mail: beristenov.samat@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12741372>

Abstract: The scientific article deals with the problems of criminal liability for involving the minors in to illegal gambling industry. The differential approach is used depending on the role of the juvenile: as a crime participant or as a member of gambling. Based on a critical assessment of the available investigations on this problem different recommendations on improving criminal legal tools to combat the organization and conduct of gambling are worked out.

Keywords: organization of gambling, minors players, gambling addiction.

When deciding the types of punishments and measures for the crimes of illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games, the courts must take into account the situation that has arisen in the activities of the bodies that carry out rapid search, inquiry and preliminary investigation activities.

In the context of a prolonged economic crisis, the draconian punishments for making too much profit from gambling will not have the expected effect. However, it is also counterintuitive to give light punishment to persons who organized, conducted and played gambling. Therefore, there is a need for punishments that are procedurally secured (implying substantial fines and actual serving of imprisonment) that are neither overly harsh nor lenient. It allows the subject to weigh his behavior, compare what he has to gain by committing the crime and what he will lose if he is prosecuted, and think about it.

There are also some problems in the application of the institution of early parole and commutation of the sentence (Articles 73 and 74 of the Uzbekistan Criminal Code[1]). In particular, it is necessary to improve the list of crimes for which it is required to determine the part of the sentence that must be served.

In recent years, there has been much talk of expanding the scope of sincere repentance. The institution of sincere remorse is of great importance in terms of activating the work of solving the crimes of illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games. The importance of the institution of sincere remorse is especially great in determining the above-mentioned cases in the

authorities, where it is difficult to identify cases of gambling and collect evidence on them. This institute performs a number of socially useful tasks. First of all, a person who sincerely repents will prevent the harmful consequences of the committed crime or compensate for the damage caused and restore the affected social relations.

According to some researchers, sincere remorse helps identify and solve gambling and other crimes, investigate them more quickly and thoroughly, and saves a lot of effort and money. The warning significance of this institution is that it provides an opportunity to prevent the commission of other crimes, to find the participants of the crime, to identify and eliminate the circumstances that led to the commission of the crime[2].

Studying the practice of using the institution of sincere remorse in the fight against the crimes of illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games allows us to conclude that this institution is correctly included in the criminal law as one of the grounds close to the exemption from criminal liability. Already, the active use of the above-mentioned institution in law enforcement practice, among other things, allowed law enforcement agencies to identify cases of organizing a number of gambling games and prosecute them.

When we talk about the problems of the crime of illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games, it is worth noting that the most problematic issue in this area is related to ensuring the effectiveness of punishment measures applied to these crimes. For example, as we mentioned above, the inconsistency of the amount of the fine as a punishment for these crimes to the committed crime (the illegal income obtained by the offender as a result of the crime) remains a serious problem. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the stability and effectiveness of the practice of combating these crimes.

We know that gambling and games of chance attract the attention of many segments of the population, including law enforcement agencies, activists, and the media, and measures aimed at combating them will be intensified. In the same process, the concept of "petty" gambling, which is committed every day and amounts to a small amount, is formed, in contrast to the illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games.

"Petty " is committed in gambling, educational institutions, enterprises and institutions, offices, and helps individuals to bypass the requirements established by law. Gradually, this crime turns into more dangerous forms of the crime of illegal organization and conduct of high-level large-scale gambling and

risk-based games. This type of gambling shows that the habit of playing in online casinos and totalizers exists in the country at all levels. There is no clear line between where "petty" gambling ends and where big gambling begins.

Focusing on the crime of illegal organization and conduct of large-scale gambling and gambling may reduce the fight against "petty" gamblers. This situation encourages us to correctly assess the impact of "small" gambling.

In order for us to properly assess the impact of small gambling, it is appropriate to consider its characteristics:

First, "petty" gambling is small and does not have a significant economic impact on many people's lives. If we imagine, demanding punishment for national traditions and customs in the people like cockfighting, ramfighting, and kopkari is a problem in itself. The reason is that as a result of this type of gambling and risk-based games, citizens often do not suffer serious losses, people do not need to apply for financial assistance, and the occurrence of various psychological diseases and stress is not recorded.

Second, "petty" gambling tends to be regressive, exacerbating economic inequality by draining resources from low-income families. This is because the rates set for "small" gambling are likely to be too high for low-income families. These "rates" limit the access of low-income families to necessary medical and educational services.

Thirdly, "petty" gambling is a type of game and domestic pastime that citizens encounter in their daily lives. It occurs mainly in neighborhoods and houses, even at market stalls, in front of law enforcement officers, and reduces citizens' trust in state law enforcement agencies.

Fourthly, the spread of "petty" gambling may in the future lead to crimes of illegal organization and conduct of large-scale gambling and risk-based games. That is, gambling is organized in a certain place, and there is a chain of officials who receive a bribe and give a part of it to a high-ranking official.

Although "petty" gambling is not considered as serious a problem as the illegal organization and operation of large-scale gambling and gambling, it has a negative impact on the daily life of ordinary people and society as a whole. As a result, people's well-being is harmed, inequality increases, public institutions weaken, and corruption is fueled.

In addition, in this regard, it is necessary to look critically at the activities of local self-government institutions. For example, a picture of the head of the finance department of Uchkoprik district of Fergana region and the district governor's assistant playing cards and betting money was spread on social

networks. In what appears to be an official office, a group of people can be seen sitting under blankets and playing cards while betting.

Gambling by a civil servant, especially when he performs this "work" in the service office, also means a gross violation of morals and disciplinary norms.

In particular, according to the "Model Rules of Ethics of State Civil Servants" approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 595 dated October 14, 2022[3], civil servants must perform their duties conscientiously, honestly and at a high professional level during their service activities, avoid formalities, forgery and it is necessary not to allow abuse, to fight with zero tolerance against any violations of the law, especially cases of corruption.

This document stipulates that civil servants must adhere to generally accepted moral standards during their free time and refrain from behavior and actions that are contrary to them.

Violation of the Code of Conduct by a civil servant is the basis for bringing them to disciplinary and other liability in accordance with the law.

On the other hand, according to Article 191 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility[4], illegal participation in gambling and other games based on risk, confiscating the items of these games, as well as the money, items and other valuable items bet on the game and winnings in the game, 3 times the amount of the basic calculated amount will result in the imposition of a fine in the amount of 1 million (990 thousand soums) to 5 times basic calculated amount (1 million 650 thousand soums).

If the same violation is repeated within a year after the application of the administrative penalty, the money, equipment and other valuables bet on the game will be confiscated, and a fine of up to 10 basic calculated amount established at the time of the commission of the administrative offense (3 million 300 thousand soums) will be applied.

In this case, the act should be studied in two parts. First of all, it should be determined where the public servants gambled, and if it is confirmed that this happened in the service room, the administration (in the form of the employer) should consider the issue of disciplinary punishment. According to the official explanation, the actions of civil servants were discussed at the meeting of the ethics commission in the presence of the governor.

Disciplinary punishment will not be enough. The photo spread in the mass media should be registered as a crime report (in the Form-1 book) in the internal affairs office, and investigations should be carried out before the

investigation. If the case is confirmed, the case should be formalized in the administrative procedure and brought to the district court for criminal cases based on the requirements of Article 245 of the Criminal Code.

It is up to the court to decide what kind of punishment to apply.

Workplace gambling is common. In most cases, officials who gambled were released from their positions when the case was confirmed. For example, in November 2022, a video of the director of the 52nd general education school in Nurota district of Navoi region and his deputy for educational affairs playing cards in the school guardroom was spread on social networks. After the situation was confirmed, the school director and his deputy were fired.

In another case, Ahror Arslanov, the chairman of Kazakh Naiman neighborhood in Pas Dargom district, was dismissed from his post after pictures of him playing gambling were spread on the Internet[5].

In order to combat petty gambling, the following is proposed:

- In order to strengthen the fight against all forms of the crime of illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games, to exclude from the Code of Administrative Responsibility the administrative offense of attracting a minor to participate in gambling and other risk-based games, and to establish criminal liability for this type of offense. must

- Amendments and additions related to the introduction of the concept of "public servants" to the provision of the crime of illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games provided for in Article 278 of the Criminal Code, that is, the social danger of gambling, the amount of profit (money) received or otherwise delivered It is appropriate to determine alternative punishments depending on the damage.

- Imprisonment should be defined as a type of criminal punishment for committing crimes related to the illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games. Since this type of punishment is aimed at educating criminals and increasing their responsibility, it is appropriate to include it in the sanction of this crime.

References:

1. Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan // <https://lex.uz/docs/111457>
2. Забарчук Е.Л. Некоторые вопросы правового обеспечения борьбы с преступностью. Вестник МГУ. Сер. "Право". – М., 1993. – С. 34.
3. Resolution Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 595 dated October 14, 2022 "On additional measures to ensure compliance with ethical rules by state civil servants" // <https://lex.uz/docs/6236840>

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

4. Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility // <https://lex.uz/docs/97661>
5. <https://kun.uz/kr/news/2023/10/25/intizomiydan-jinoiygacha-qimor-oynaganlik-uchun-qanday-jazo-bor>